

EOSC-Future Test Science Project "META-COVID": Linked resources between BBMRI-ERIC Directory and ECRIN Metadata Repository

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ECRIN = European Clinical Research Infrastructure Network, Paris, France

BBMRI-ERIC = Biobanking and Biomolecular Resources Research Infrastructure – European Research Infrastructure Consortium, Graz, Austria

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Within the EOSC-Future TSP "META-COVID", a use case has been developed to bridge resources between ECRIN Metadata Repository (MDR) and BBMRI-ERIC Directory. The BBMRI-ERIC Directory (<https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu>) collects information about biobanks throughout Europe as well as the biosample collections and data they make available for research (currently, over 400 biobanks are registered, collectively making available over 1400 sample collections). The ECRIN MDR (<https://new-mdr.ecrin.org/>) is based upon the ECRIN metadata schema and contains metadata from 800,000 clinical research studies and 1.3 million digital objects related to these studies. Collections registered in the BBMRI-ERIC Directory may have been created within a clinical study or trial registered in the ECRIN MDR, however a direct link between the collection and the clinical study or trial has usually not been implemented and cannot be used to merge related information, which belongs together and may considerably enrich the metadata of the BBMRI-ERIC Directory and the ECRIN MDR. In this document those collections registered in the BBMRI-ERIC Directory collections are listed that could be linked to a related study or trial registered in the ECRIN MDR. The full project will be published in Open Research Europe. The EOSC Future project is co-funded by the European Union Horizon Programme call INFRAEOSC-03-2020 - Grant Agreement Number 101017536.

A1. Initial Mapping - largely manual

Initial mapping started in the BBMRI-ERIC Directory using the full-text searching capabilities of the catalogue to search for any terms possibly related to clinical trials/clinical studies. The search for "clinical trial" identified 135 collections, of which 58 collections could be mapped to one of 37 COVID-related clinical trials.

Collection in BBMRI Directory (URL)	Mapped clinical trial (URL)
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-200:collection:1	https://clinicaltrials.gov/ct2/show/study/NCT02315716
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-145:collection:389-1098	https://www.isrctn.com/ISRCTN50083238
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-145:collection:389-1099	
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-145:collection:389-1100	

https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-145:collection:389-1101	
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-145:collection:389-1102	
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-145:collection:389-1103	
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-145:collection:388-1090	https://clinicaltrials.gov/ct2/show/study/NCT02308722
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-145:collection:388-1091	
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-145:collection:388-1092	
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-145:collection:388-1093	
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-145:collection:388-1094	
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-145:collection:388-1095	
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-145:collection:390-1104	
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-145:collection:390-1105	
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-145:collection:390-1106	
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-145:collection:390-1107	
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-145:collection:391-1108	https://clinicaltrials.gov/ct2/show/study/NCT03529669
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-145:collection:391-1109	
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-145:collection:391-1110	
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-145:collection:391-1111	
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-145:collection:396-1122	https://clinicaltrials.gov/ct2/show/study/NCT00357682
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-145:collection:396-1123	

https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-145:collection:396-1124	
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-145:collection:396-1125	
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:CH_UniversitatsspitalBasel:collection:CH_MATAO	https://clinicaltrials.gov/ct2/show/study/NCT04111978
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-119:collection:310-880	https://clinicaltrials.gov/ct2/show/study/NCT01303887
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-119:collection:310-881	
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-179:collection:1	https://clinicaltrials.gov/ct2/show/study/NCT03562169
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-35:collection:193-582	https://www.isrctn.com/ISRCTN44687907
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-35:collection:193-583	
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:AT_MUW:collection:BB9315	https://clinicaltrials.gov/ct2/show/study/NCT00994318
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_AMCBB:collection:AB20-012	https://clinicaltrials.gov/ct2/show/study/NCT03961438
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-24:collection:1	https://clinicaltrials.gov/ct2/show/study/NCT00749450
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-104:collection:1	https://www.isrctn.com/ISRCTN84013636
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-151:collection:1	https://clinicaltrials.gov/ct2/show/study/NCT01654146
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-191:collection:1	https://clinicaltrials.gov/ct2/show/study/NCT00112931
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_CRC:collection:10012	https://trialregister.nl/trial/7277
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_AAAACXSW447PSACQK2MBZ5YAAM:collection:AAAACXSW47D4CACQK2MBZ5YAAE	https://www.clinicaltrialsregister.eu/ctr-search/trial/2016-002493-13/NL
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_AAAACXSW447PSACQK2MBZ5YAAM:collection:AAAACYBR6IJTWACQK2MBZ5YAAE	https://clinicaltrials.gov/ct2/show/study/NCT02826512
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_CRC:collection:10006	https://trialregister.nl/trial/8261

https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_CRC:collection:10034	https://clinicaltrials.gov/ct2/show/study/NCT02945566
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_CRC:collection:10026	https://www.clinicaltrialsregister.eu/ctr-search/trial/2013-003489-15/IT
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_CRC:collection:10019	https://clinicaltrials.gov/ct2/show/study/NCT03737539 (some remaining uncertainty)
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_CRC:collection:10031	http://www.drks.de/DRKS00011917
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_CRC:collection:10033	https://clinicaltrials.gov/ct2/show/results/NCT02231086
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-134:collection:1	https://clinicaltrials.gov/ct2/show/study/NCT02057913
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:DE_UMGB:collection:BioVAT-HF	https://clinicaltrials.gov/ct2/show/study/NCT04396899 (NCT number in description of collection)
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:DE_UMGB:collection:ROCK-ALS	https://clinicaltrials.gov/ct2/show/study/NCT03792490 (NCT number in description of collection)
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_CRC:collection:10023	https://www.trialregister.nl/trial/8177
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_CRC:collection:10032	https://clinicaltrials.gov/ct2/show/study/NCT02070146
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:DE_IBBJ:collection:TARGET	http://www.drks.de/DRKS00011023
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_AAAACXSW447PSACQK2MBZ5YAAM:collection:AAAACXSW45URYACQK2MBZ5YAAE	https://www.clinicaltrialsregister.eu/ctr-search/trial/2015-001969-49/NL
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_CRC:collection:10030	https://clinicaltrials.gov/ct2/show/study/NCT02371304
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_AMCBB:collection:AB16-005	https://www.isrctn.com/ISRCTN48151589
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-123:collection:1	https://clinicaltrials.gov/ct2/show/study/NCT00058032
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_AAAACXSW447PSACQK2MBZ5YAAM:collection:AAAACXSW46HH4ACQK2MBZ5YAAE	https://clinicaltrials.gov/ct2/show/study/NCT02925234
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_AMCBB:collection:AB17-001	https://trialregister.nl/trial/280

A2. Second Mapping, using Acronyms

Often clinical studies are labelled with a specific acronym. For that reason, acronyms of clinical studies in the MDR were identified and then searched in the BBMRI database. The results were disappointing, only 7 studies were identified this way.

No	BBMRI URL	MDR
1	https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/menu/main/app-molgenis-app-bio-bank-explorer#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:AT_MUG:collection:COVAC-DMStudy:diabetesmellitustype1diabetesmellitustype2COVID-19COVID-19vaccine	https://www.clinicaltrialsregister.eu/ctr-search/trial/2021-001459-15/AT
2	https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/menu/main/app-molgenis-app-bio-bank-explorer#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_AAAACW5FCXM3MZSU-AVNCZ2AAAE:collection:EMC_CB_IMPORT_2021_05	https://www.clinicaltrialsregister.eu/ctr-search/trial/2021-001054-57/NL
3	https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/menu/main/app-molgenis-app-bio-bank-explorer#/?search=COVVA	https://clinicaltrials.gov/ct2/show/study/NCT04858607
		https://clinicaltrials.gov/ct2/show/study/NCT05142540
4	https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/menu/main/app-molgenis-app-bio-bank-explorer#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_AMCBB:collection:AB21-003	Trial could not be identified. (Dutch)
5	https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/menu/main/app-molgenis-app-bio-bank-explorer#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_AAAACVOEPHI3IZSU-AVNCZ2AAAE:collection:DC14-001	Trial could not be identified.
6	https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/menu/main/app-molgenis-app-bio-bank-explorer#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_RB:collection:154	Trial could not be identified. (Dutch)
7	https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/menu/main/app-molgenis-app-bio-bank-explorer#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_AAAACXPF7SE-QEACQK2ME25QAAE:collection:29	Trial could not be identified. (Dutch)
8	https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/menu/main/app-molgenis-app-bio-bank-explorer#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_AMCBB:collection:AB21-009	https://www.clinicaltrialsregister.eu/ctr-search/trial/2021-002327-38/NL

9	https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/menu/main/app-molgenis-app-bio-bank-explorer#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:AT_MUG:collection:TheCoVVacStudy:COVID-19vaccinationimmunocompromised-healthy-cellagingt-cellimmunityhumoralandcellularimmuneresponse	Redundant
10	https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/menu/main/app-molgenis-app-bio-bank-explorer#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_AMCBB:collection:AB21-022	https://www.clinicaltrialsregister.eu/ctr-search/trial/2021-005051-37/NL
11	https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/menu/main/app-molgenis-app-bio-bank-explorer#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_AAAACW5FCXM3MZSU-AVNCZ2AAAE:collection:EMC_2023_6535	https://www.clinicaltrialsregister.eu/ctr-search/trial/2021-001072-41/NL
12	bbmri-eric:ID:NL_AAAACXPF7SE-QEACQK2ME25QAAE	Trial could not be identified. (Dutch)
13	bbmri-eric:ID:NL_AMCBB	No specific trial
14	https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/menu/main/app-molgenis-app-bio-bank-explorer#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_AAAACW5FCXM3MZSU-AVNCZ2AAAE:collection:imaging_smartmr	Trial could not be identified.

A3. Third Mapping, using systematic search

A systematic search of the public BBMRI-ERIC Directory was made (i.e. all biobanks and collections). Using the collection name, and then description, collections were identified that, at least potentially, were linked to clinical research studies. Then, to unambiguously match registered sample collections to specific registered studies, a defined stepwise and manual procedure was executed, which resulted in 202 clinical studies linked to 284 collections.

Collection in BBMRI Directory (URL)	study identifier	MDR Title
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-190:collection:1	2007-006064-30	A randomised phase III trial to assess response adapted therapy using FDG-PET imaging in patients with newly diagnosed, advanced Hodgkin Lymphoma
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-119:collection:306-875	2008-006342-25	ADMIRE: Does the ADDition of Mitoxantrone Improve REsponse to FCR chemotherapy in patients with CLL: A randomised Phase II Trial of fludarabine, cyclophosphamide and rituximab (FCR) with or without mitoxantrone (M)
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-119:collection:306-876	2008-006342-25	ADMIRE: Does the ADDition of Mitoxantrone Improve REsponse to FCR chemotherapy in patients with CLL: A randomised Phase II Trial of fludarabine, cyclophosphamide and rituximab (FCR) with or without mitoxantrone (M)
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-119:collection:306-875	2010-022260-12	CLL Empirical Antibiotic Regimen
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-119:collection:306-876	2010-022260-12	CLL Empirical Antibiotic Regimen
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-153:collection:362-1020	2010-023083-40	Chemotherapy then Radiation then Immediate Curative Surgery for operable rectal cancer

Collection in BBMRI Directory (URL)	study identifier	MDR Title
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-153:collection:362-1021	2010-023083-40	Chemotherapy then Radiation then Immediate Curative Surgery for operable rectal cancer
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-153:collection:362-1022	2010-023083-40	Chemotherapy then Radiation then Immediate Curative Surgery for operable rectal cancer
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-153:collection:362-1023	2010-023083-40	Chemotherapy then Radiation then Immediate Curative Surgery for operable rectal cancer
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-119:collection:306-875	2011-000796-14	COSMIC: Chemotherapy plus Ofatumumab at Standard or Mega dose In CLL
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-119:collection:306-876	2011-000796-14	COSMIC: Chemotherapy plus Ofatumumab at Standard or Mega dose In CLL
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-119:collection:306-875	2011-000919-22	A trial to compare the safety and effectiveness of ofatumumab when given in combination with two different chemotherapy drugs called chlorambucil and bendamustine.
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-119:collection:306-876	2011-000919-22	A trial to compare the safety and effectiveness of ofatumumab when given in combination with two different chemotherapy drugs called chlorambucil and bendamustine.
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:AT_MUW:collection:BB9272BB9297	2012-001824-36	ORAL SODIUM BICARBONATE SUPPLEMENTATION IN PATIENTS WITH CHRONIC METABOLIC ACIDOSIS AND CHRONIC KIDNEY DISEASE
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:AT_MUW:collection:BB9272BB9297	2012-001824-36	ORAL SODIUM BICARBONATE SUPPLEMENTATION IN PATIENTS WITH

Collection in BBMRI Directory (URL)	study identifier	MDR Title
eric.ID:AT_MUW:collection:BB9272BB9297:328365		CHRONIC METABOLIC ACIDOSIS AND CHRONIC KIDNEY DISEASE
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric.ID:AT_MUW:collection:BB9272BB9297:328366	2012-001824-36	ORAL SODIUM BICARBONATE SUPPLEMENTATION IN PATIENTS WITH CHRONIC METABOLIC ACIDOSIS AND CHRONIC KIDNEY DISEASE
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric.ID:AT_MUW:collection:BB9272BB9297:328367	2012-001824-36	ORAL SODIUM BICARBONATE SUPPLEMENTATION IN PATIENTS WITH CHRONIC METABOLIC ACIDOSIS AND CHRONIC KIDNEY DISEASE
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric.ID:AT_MUW:collection:BB9272BB9297:328368	2012-001824-36	ORAL SODIUM BICARBONATE SUPPLEMENTATION IN PATIENTS WITH CHRONIC METABOLIC ACIDOSIS AND CHRONIC KIDNEY DISEASE
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric.ID:NL_AAAACXSW447PSACQK2MBZ5YAAM:collection:AAAACXSW45URYACQK2MBZ5YAAE	2015-001969-49	Phase II study with nivolumab (anti-PD1) in patients with triple negative breast cancer after induction treatment.
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric.ID:NL_AAAACXSW447PSACQK2MBZ5YAAM:collection:AAAACXSW47D4CACQK2MBZ5YAAE	2016-002493-13	Substantially improving the cure rate of high-risk BRCA1-like breast cancer patients with personalized therapy
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric.ID:UK_GBR-1-192:collection:486-1349	2017-000161-75	Study Evaluating the Efficacy of Maintenance Olaparib and Cediranib or Olaparib Alone in Ovarian Cancer Patients.
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric.ID:NL_AMCBB:collection:AB20-002	2017-004737-85	Alkaline Phosphatase to prevent ischemia reperfusion injury in living kidney transplantation
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric.ID:NL_AAAACW5FCXM3MZSUAVNCZ2AAAE:collection:EMC_CB_IMPORT_2021_05	2021-001054-57	SARS-CoV-2 vaccination response in people living with HIV

Collection in BBMRI Directory (URL)	study identifier	MDR Title
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_AAAACW5FCXM3MZSUAVNCZ2AAAE:collection:EMC_2023_6535	2021-001072-41	COBRA-KAI study: COVID-19 vaccination in patients with a hematological disease
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:AT_MUG:collection:COVAC-DMStudy:diabetesmellitustype1diabetesmellitustype2COVID-19COVID-19vaccine	2021-001459-15	Immune response to COVID-19 Vaccination in people with Diabetes Mellitus
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_AMCBB:collection:AB21-009	2021-002327-38	PREGCOVAC-19: the follow up of pregnant women who received COVID-19 vaccination in the Dutch national vaccination program
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_AMCBB:collection:AB21-022	2021-005051-37	a cohort study for the evaluation of the use of neutralizing monoclonal SARS-CoV-2 antibodies
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:DE_HUB:collection:REBIRTH-AW	DRKS00005159	Improvement of endogenous regeneration in female healthy volunteers through physical exercise REBIRTH aktiv women”
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:DE_IBBJ:collection:TARGET	DRKS00011023	Therapeutic drug Monitoring (TDM) of piperacillin in patients with fever in neutropenia in the course of myelosuppressive cytostatic chemotherapy
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_CRC:collection:10031	DRKS00011917	Color III: a multicentre randomised clinical Trial comparing transanal TME versus laparoscopic TME for mid an low rectal cancer, Phase 3
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:DE_UMGB:collection:TEACH	DRKS00020824	Efficacy of team-based care for distressed patients in secondary prevention of chronic coronary heart disease: a randomized controlled trial
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-	ISRCTN01844152	Front-line therapy in CLL: assessment of ibrutinib-containing regimes

Collection in BBMRI Directory (URL)	study identifier	MDR Title
eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-119:collection:306-875		
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-119:collection:306-876	ISRCTN01844152	Front-line therapy in CLL: assessment of ibrutinib-containing regimes
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-52:collection:397-1128	ISRCTN10079972	DIAPHRAGM: Diagnostic and prognostic biomarkers in the rational assessment of mesothelioma
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-52:collection:397-1129	ISRCTN10079972	DIAPHRAGM: Diagnostic and prognostic biomarkers in the rational assessment of mesothelioma
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-52:collection:397-1130	ISRCTN10079972	DIAPHRAGM: Diagnostic and prognostic biomarkers in the rational assessment of mesothelioma
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-91:collection:1	ISRCTN15004993	Effect of Peri-operative anti-HER2 therapy On early breast cancer Study - Biological phase
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-85:collection:1	ISRCTN15124653	TOPARP: A Phase II Trial of Olaparib in Patients With Advanced Castration Resistant Prostate Cancer
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_AAAACVOEPHI3IZSUAVNCZ2AAAE:collection:DC18-001	ISRCTN15255286	ARREST registry: Amsterdam resuscitation studies
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_AAAACXPKMVPYIACQK2ME25QAAE:collection:92	ISRCTN15255286	ARREST registry: Amsterdam resuscitation studies
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-119:collection:306-875	ISRCTN16544962	Attenuated dose rituximab with chemotherapy in chronic lymphocytic leukaemia (CLL)

Collection in BBMRI Directory (URL)	study identifier	MDR Title
eric.ID:UK_GBR-1-119:collection:306-875		
https://directory.bbMRI-eric.eu/#/collection/bbMRI-eric.ID:UK_GBR-1-119:collection:306-876	ISRCTN16544962	Attenuated dose rituximab with chemotherapy in chronic lymphocytic leukaemia (CLL)
https://directory.bbMRI-eric.eu/#/collection/bbMRI-eric.ID:UK_GBR-1-93:collection:1	ISRCTN17168679	Enzalutamide (MDV3100) in combination with AZD5363 in patients with metastatic castration-resistant prostate cancer
https://directory.bbMRI-eric.eu/#/collection/bbMRI-eric.ID:UK_GBR-1-250:collection:1	ISRCTN17170034	Can Patients with Residual Cancer After Chemotherapy for Early Breast Cancer be Identified With Multiple Ultrasound-guided Biopsies?
https://directory.bbMRI-eric.eu/#/collection/bbMRI-eric.ID:UK_GBR-1-123:collection:323-905	ISRCTN22488978	UK Collaborative Trial of Ovarian Cancer Screening (UKCTOCS) and the long-term impact of screening on ovarian cancer mortality in UKCTOCS
https://directory.bbMRI-eric.eu/#/collection/bbMRI-eric.ID:UK_GBR-1-123:collection:324-906	ISRCTN22488978	UK Collaborative Trial of Ovarian Cancer Screening (UKCTOCS) and the long-term impact of screening on ovarian cancer mortality in UKCTOCS
https://directory.bbMRI-eric.eu/#/collection/bbMRI-eric.ID:UK_GBR-1-123:collection:325-907	ISRCTN22488978	UK Collaborative Trial of Ovarian Cancer Screening (UKCTOCS) and the long-term impact of screening on ovarian cancer mortality in UKCTOCS
https://directory.bbMRI-eric.eu/#/collection/bbMRI-eric.ID:UK_GBR-1-123:collection:326-908	ISRCTN22488978	UK Collaborative Trial of Ovarian Cancer Screening (UKCTOCS) and the long-term impact of screening on ovarian cancer mortality in UKCTOCS
https://directory.bbMRI-eric.eu/#/collection/bbMRI-eric.ID:UK_GBR-1-123:collection:329-911	ISRCTN22488978	UK Collaborative Trial of Ovarian Cancer Screening (UKCTOCS) and the long-term impact of screening on ovarian cancer mortality in UKCTOCS
https://directory.bbMRI-eric.eu/#/collection/bbMRI-eric.ID:UK_GBR-1-123:collection:329-911	ISRCTN22488978	UK Collaborative Trial of Ovarian Cancer Screening (UKCTOCS) and the long-term impact of screening on ovarian cancer mortality in UKCTOCS

Collection in BBMRI Directory (URL)	study identifier	MDR Title
eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-123:collection:330-912		impact of screening on ovarian cancer mortality in UKCTOCS
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-123:collection:331-914	ISRCTN22488978	UK Collaborative Trial of Ovarian Cancer Screening (UKCTOCS) and the long-term impact of screening on ovarian cancer mortality in UKCTOCS
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-123:collection:518-1514	ISRCTN22488978	UK Collaborative Trial of Ovarian Cancer Screening (UKCTOCS) and the long-term impact of screening on ovarian cancer mortality in UKCTOCS
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-123:collection:519-1515	ISRCTN22488978	UK Collaborative Trial of Ovarian Cancer Screening (UKCTOCS) and the long-term impact of screening on ovarian cancer mortality in UKCTOCS
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-123:collection:521-1516	ISRCTN22488978	UK Collaborative Trial of Ovarian Cancer Screening (UKCTOCS) and the long-term impact of screening on ovarian cancer mortality in UKCTOCS
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_AAAACXPK6TQCOACQK2ME25QAAE:collection:100	ISRCTN26257579	The Hoorn Diabetes Care System cohort (DCS): an observational prospective cohort study
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_AMCBB:collection:AB17-017	ISRCTN30518857	Levodopa in early Parkinsons disease
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_AAAACXPF4VZU4ACQK2ME25QAAM:collection:195	ISRCTN31493512	The New Hoorn Study
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:AT_MUG:collection:EPATHstudy	ISRCTN33941607	Effects of eplerenone in patients with primary hyperparathyroidism
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:DE_HUB:collection:ProBase	ISRCTN37591328	Risk-adapted prostate cancer (PCa) early detection study based on a “baseline”

Collection in BBMRI Directory (URL)	study identifier	MDR Title
		PSA value in young men – a prospective multicenter randomized trial (PROBASE)
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-90:collection:1	ISRCTN39058880	Nilotinib in the Treatment of c-KIT Mutated Melanoma (NICAM)
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-119:collection:306-875	ISRCTN40303610	Phase II trial of alemtuzumab, dexamethasone and lenalidomide followed by randomisation to lenalidomide maintenance versus no further treatment for high-risk CLL (NCRICLL210)
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-119:collection:306-876	ISRCTN40303610	Phase II trial of alemtuzumab, dexamethasone and lenalidomide followed by randomisation to lenalidomide maintenance versus no further treatment for high-risk CLL (NCRICLL210)
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_AAAACVOEPHI3IZSUAVNCZ2AAAE:collection:DC09-002	ISRCTN40976937	PROspective Study of Pravastatin in the Elderly at Risk (PROSPER)
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-35:collection:193-582	ISRCTN44687907	Alternative chemotherapy for frail or elderly patients with advanced gastric or oesophageal cancer
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-35:collection:193-583	ISRCTN44687907	Alternative chemotherapy for frail or elderly patients with advanced gastric or oesophageal cancer
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-209:collection:1	ISRCTN47127434	PHOENIX: A trial to look for markers in the tumour cells and blood which signal that trial drugs are working in a patient with triple negative breast cancer, for whom upfront chemotherapy has not provided the maximum expected benefit
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-247:collection:1	ISRCTN47437448	Randomised trial testing dose escalated intensity modulated radiotherapy in women with higher than average local tumour recurrence risk after breast

Collection in BBMRI Directory (URL)	study identifier	MDR Title
		conservation therapy for early breast cancer
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-153:collection:358-1010	ISRCTN47718479	Cisplatin, Capecitabine, and Radiation Therapy With or Without Cetuximab in Treating Patients With Esophageal Cancer
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-153:collection:358-1011	ISRCTN47718479	Cisplatin, Capecitabine, and Radiation Therapy With or Without Cetuximab in Treating Patients With Esophageal Cancer
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_AMCBB:collection:AB16-005	ISRCTN48151589	Healthy aging through internet counseling in the elderly
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-145:collection:389-1098	ISRCTN50083238	Systemic Therapy and Chemoradiation in Advanced Localised Pancreatic Cancer - 2
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-145:collection:389-1099	ISRCTN50083238	Systemic Therapy and Chemoradiation in Advanced Localised Pancreatic Cancer - 2
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-145:collection:389-1100	ISRCTN50083238	Systemic Therapy and Chemoradiation in Advanced Localised Pancreatic Cancer - 2
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-145:collection:389-1101	ISRCTN50083238	Systemic Therapy and Chemoradiation in Advanced Localised Pancreatic Cancer - 2
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-145:collection:389-1102	ISRCTN50083238	Systemic Therapy and Chemoradiation in Advanced Localised Pancreatic Cancer - 2
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-	ISRCTN50083238	Systemic Therapy and Chemoradiation in Advanced Localised Pancreatic Cancer - 2

Collection in BBMRI Directory (URL)	study identifier	MDR Title
eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-145:collection:389-1103		
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_AAAACW5FCXM3MZSUAVNCZ2AAAE:collection:imaging_nelson	ISRCTN63545820	Dutch Belgian randomised lung cancer screening trial (NELSON)
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-92:collection:1	ISRCTN63733470	A Trial of Cediranib in the Treatment of Patients With Alveolar Soft Part Sarcoma (CASPS)
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-89:collection:1	ISRCTN63882543	Trial of Perioperative Endocrine Therapy - Individualising Care
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-189:collection:1	ISRCTN66541317	Standard Chemotherapy With or Without Nelarabine or Rituximab in Treating Patients With Newly Diagnosed Acute Lymphoblastic Leukemia
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-178:collection:1	ISRCTN78818544	Systemic Therapy in Advancing or Metastatic Prostate Cancer: Evaluation of Drug Efficacy
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-176:collection:1	ISRCTN80416929	ION - Is ablative radiOiodine Necessary for low risk differentiated thyroid cancer patients?
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-153:collection:359-1012	ISRCTN80812769	FRAGMATIC - A Randomised Phase III Clinical Trial Investigating the Effect of FRAGMin Added to Standard Therapy In Patients With Lung Cancer
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-153:collection:359-1013	ISRCTN80812769	FRAGMATIC - A Randomised Phase III Clinical Trial Investigating the Effect of FRAGMin Added to Standard Therapy In Patients With Lung Cancer
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-104:collection:1	ISRCTN84013636	Photodynamic versus white light-guided treatment of non-muscle invasive bladder cancer

Collection in BBMRI Directory (URL)	study identifier	MDR Title
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-104:collection:530-1531	ISRCTN84013636	Photodynamic versus white light-guided treatment of non-muscle invasive bladder cancer
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-119:collection:306-875	ISRCTN88860946	Single arm NCRI feasibility study of Cyclophosphamide, Hydroxydaunorubicin, Oncovin, Prednisone (CHOP) in combination with Ofatumumab in induction and maintenance for patients with newly diagnosed Richters syndrome
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-119:collection:306-876	ISRCTN88860946	Single arm NCRI feasibility study of Cyclophosphamide, Hydroxydaunorubicin, Oncovin, Prednisone (CHOP) in combination with Ofatumumab in induction and maintenance for patients with newly diagnosed Richters syndrome
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-136:collection:1	ISRCTN89118367	Docetaxel with or without AZD6244 in wt BRAF advanced melanoma
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-183:collection:1	ISRCTN92154110	Window study of the PARP inhibitor rucaparib in patients with primary triple negative or BRCA1/2 related breast cancer (RIO)
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-153:collection:360-1014	ISRCTN96169987	Selective Chemoradiation in Advanced Localised Pancreatic cancer
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-153:collection:360-1015	ISRCTN96169987	Selective Chemoradiation in Advanced Localised Pancreatic cancer
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-86:collection:1	ISRCTN97330959	Triple Negative Trial: a randomised phase III trial of carboplatin compared to docetaxel for patients with advanced oestrogen receptor-progesterone receptor-human epidermal growth factor receptor two-breast cancer

Collection in BBMRI Directory (URL)	study identifier	MDR Title
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-122:collection:307-877	ISRCTN98496463	Validating predictive models and biomarkers of radiotherapy toxicity to reduce side effects and improve quality of life in cancer survivors
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-122:collection:308-878	ISRCTN98496463	Validating predictive models and biomarkers of radiotherapy toxicity to reduce side effects and improve quality of life in cancer survivors
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-122:collection:309-879	ISRCTN98496463	Validating predictive models and biomarkers of radiotherapy toxicity to reduce side effects and improve quality of life in cancer survivors
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_AAAACXPF3ZSUWACQK2ME25QAAM:collection:160	NCT00032136	Tamoxifen and Exemestane Adjuvant Multicenter trial.
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-123:collection:1	NCT00058032	CA125 and Ultrasound in Detecting Ovarian Cancer in Postmenopausal Women
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-191:collection:1	NCT00112931	Rituximab in Treating Patients With Newly Diagnosed Stage II, Stage III, or Stage IV Follicular Non-Hodgkin's Lymphoma
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_AAAACW5ELBQ4WZSUAVNCZ2AAAE:collection:80	NCT00127452	Alpha Omega Trial: Study of Omega-3 Fatty Acids and Coronary Mortality
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:DE_IBBJ:collection:VISEP	NCT00135473	Efficacy of Volume Substitution and Insulin Therapy in Severe Sepsis (VISEP Trial)
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_AAAACVOEPHI3ZSUAVNCZ2AAAE:collection:DC09-003	NCT00166530	EASEGO Study: Doubling of Atorvastatin/Simvastatin or INEGY in Patients With Hypercholesterolemia and Coronary Artery Disease(CAD)(0653A-089)

Collection in BBMRI Directory (URL)	study identifier	MDR Title
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_CRC:collection:10037	NCT00208546	Cetuximab, Capecitabine, Oxaliplatin and Bevacizumab in Advanced Colorectal Cancer
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:SE_2326:collection:all_samples	NCT00279318	TEDDY - The Environmental Determinants of Diabetes in the Young
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:SE_Region_Skanes_Biobank:collection:TEDDY	NCT00279318	TEDDY - The Environmental Determinants of Diabetes in the Young
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_CRC:collection:10036	NCT00312000	Sequential Versus Combination Chemotherapy in Advanced Colorectal Carcinoma
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:FI_002:collection:ATBC	NCT00342992	Alpha-Tocopherol, Beta-Carotene Cancer Prevention (ATBC) Study
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-145:collection:396-1122	NCT00357682	A Phase III, Randomized, Study of Aspirin and Esomeprazole Chemoprevention in Barrett's Metaplasia
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-145:collection:396-1123	NCT00357682	A Phase III, Randomized, Study of Aspirin and Esomeprazole Chemoprevention in Barrett's Metaplasia
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-145:collection:396-1124	NCT00357682	A Phase III, Randomized, Study of Aspirin and Esomeprazole Chemoprevention in Barrett's Metaplasia
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-145:collection:396-1125	NCT00357682	A Phase III, Randomized, Study of Aspirin and Esomeprazole Chemoprevention in Barrett's Metaplasia
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_AMCBB:collection:AB17-016	NCT00362661	Low-dose Cortisol in Chronic Posttraumatic Stress Disorder

Collection in BBMRI Directory (URL)	study identifier	MDR Title
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_CRC:collection:10038	NCT00442637	Maintenance Treatment Versus Observation After Induction in Advanced Colorectal Carcinoma
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:DE_IBBJ:collection:MAXSEP	NCT00534287	Comparison of Two Antibiotic Regimen (Meropenem Versus Meropenem+Moxifloxacin)in the Treatment of Severe Sepsis and Septic Shock
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-106:collection:289-847	NCT00601406	Study of DNA Mutations in Predicting the Effect of External-Beam Radiation Therapy in Patients With Early Breast Cancer, Localized Prostate Cancer, or Gynecological Cancer
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-106:collection:290-843	NCT00601406	Study of DNA Mutations in Predicting the Effect of External-Beam Radiation Therapy in Patients With Early Breast Cancer, Localized Prostate Cancer, or Gynecological Cancer
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-106:collection:291-846	NCT00601406	Study of DNA Mutations in Predicting the Effect of External-Beam Radiation Therapy in Patients With Early Breast Cancer, Localized Prostate Cancer, or Gynecological Cancer
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-106:collection:292-845	NCT00601406	Study of DNA Mutations in Predicting the Effect of External-Beam Radiation Therapy in Patients With Early Breast Cancer, Localized Prostate Cancer, or Gynecological Cancer
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:DE_IBBJ:collection:HYPRESS	NCT00670254	Hydrocortisone for Prevention of Septic Shock
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-24:collection:1	NCT00749450	Combination Chemotherapy After Surgery in Treating Patients With High-Risk Stage II or Stage III Colorectal Cancer

Collection in BBMRI Directory (URL)	study identifier	MDR Title
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:DE_IBBJ:collection:SISPCT	NCT00832039	Placebo Controlled Trial of Sodium Selenite and Procalcitonin Guided Antimicrobial Therapy in Severe Sepsis
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:AT_MUW:collection:BB9315	NCT00994318	Ferric Carboxymaltose (FCM) Assessment in Subjects With Iron Deficiency Anaemia and Non-dialysis-dependent Chronic Kidney Disease (NDD-CKD)
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:AT_MUW:collection:BB9033	NCT01045031	Cognitive Function in Elderly Marathon Runners
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:AT_MUW:collection:BB9033:328303	NCT01045031	Cognitive Function in Elderly Marathon Runners
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:AT_MUW:collection:BB9033:328304	NCT01045031	Cognitive Function in Elderly Marathon Runners
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:AT_MUW:collection:BB9033:328305	NCT01045031	Cognitive Function in Elderly Marathon Runners
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:AT_MUW:collection:BB9033:328306	NCT01045031	Cognitive Function in Elderly Marathon Runners
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_NA:collection:aaaacyi5i2dcx6qwh3e73dqaae	NCT01217307	Metformin to Reduce Heart Failure After Myocardial Infarction
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-148:collection:369-1032	NCT01238380	Using Pharmacogenetics to Improve Treatment in Early-onset Diabetes

Collection in BBMRI Directory (URL)	study identifier	MDR Title
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-148:collection:369-1033	NCT01238380	Using Pharmacogenetics to Improve Treatment in Early-onset Diabetes
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-148:collection:369-1034	NCT01238380	Using Pharmacogenetics to Improve Treatment in Early-onset Diabetes
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-148:collection:369-1035	NCT01238380	Using Pharmacogenetics to Improve Treatment in Early-onset Diabetes
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-148:collection:369-1036	NCT01238380	Using Pharmacogenetics to Improve Treatment in Early-onset Diabetes
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-148:collection:369-1037	NCT01238380	Using Pharmacogenetics to Improve Treatment in Early-onset Diabetes
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-148:collection:369-1038	NCT01238380	Using Pharmacogenetics to Improve Treatment in Early-onset Diabetes
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-148:collection:369-1039	NCT01238380	Using Pharmacogenetics to Improve Treatment in Early-onset Diabetes
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-148:collection:369-1040	NCT01238380	Using Pharmacogenetics to Improve Treatment in Early-onset Diabetes
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-148:collection:369-1041	NCT01238380	Using Pharmacogenetics to Improve Treatment in Early-onset Diabetes

Collection in BBMRI Directory (URL)	study identifier	MDR Title
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-148:collection:369-1042	NCT01238380	Using Pharmacogenetics to Improve Treatment in Early-onset Diabetes
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-148:collection:369-1043	NCT01238380	Using Pharmacogenetics to Improve Treatment in Early-onset Diabetes
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-119:collection:310-880	NCT01303887	A Trial Looking at Rituximab and Chemotherapy as a Treatment for Follicular Lymphoma in Elderly Patients
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-119:collection:310-881	NCT01303887	A Trial Looking at Rituximab and Chemotherapy as a Treatment for Follicular Lymphoma in Elderly Patients
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_AAAACXSW447PSACQK2MBZ5YAAM:collection:AAAACXSW45IHAACQK2MBZ5YAAM	NCT01408004	Rotating Pazopanib and Everolimus to Avoid Resistance (ROPETAR)
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:SE_Region_Skanes_Biobank:collection:MEDIM	NCT01420198	A Middle Eastern Immigrant Population At-risk for Diabetes; Contributing Risk Factors and the Efficiency and Cost-effectiveness of a Culturally Adopted Lifestyle Intervention Program - the MEDIM Study.
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_CRC:collection:10025	NCT01558921	Rectal Cancer and Pre-operative Induction Therapy Followed by Dedicated Operation. The RAPIDO Trial
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_AAAACW5FCXM3MZSUAVNCZ2AAAE:collection:cairo4	NCT01606098	The Role of Surgery of the Primary Tumour in Patients with Synchronous Unresectable Metastases of Colorectal Cancer

Collection in BBMRI Directory (URL)	study identifier	MDR Title
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_CRC:collection:10001	NCT01606098	The Role of Surgery of the Primary Tumour in Patients With Synchronous Unresectable Metastases of Colorectal Cancer
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-151:collection:1	NCT01654146	ICON8: Weekly Chemotherapy in Ovarian Cancer
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-188:collection:1	NCT01679119	Treatment of Patients with Diffuse Large B Cell Lymphoma Who Are Not Suitable for Anthracycline Containing Chemotherapy
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_AAAACW5FCXM3MZSUAVNCZ2AAAE:collection:96	NCT01789411	The European Collaborative Project on Inflammation and Vascular Wall Remodeling in Atherosclerosis - Intravascular Ultrasound Study
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_CRC:collection:10026	NCT01792934	Chemotherapy and Maximal Tumor Debulking of Multi-organ Colorectal Cancer Metastases
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-184:collection:1	NCT01805271	Randomized, double-blind, multicentric phase III trial evaluating the safety and benefit of adding everolimus to adjuvant hormone therapy in women with poor prognosis, ER+ and HER2- primary breast cancer who remain free of disease after receiving 3 years of adjuvant hormone therapy
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-153:collection:361-1016	NCT01843829	A Feasibility Study of Chemo-radiotherapy to Treat Operable Oesophageal Cancer
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-153:collection:361-1017	NCT01843829	A Feasibility Study of Chemo-radiotherapy to Treat Operable Oesophageal Cancer
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-153:collection:361-1016	NCT01843829	A Feasibility Study of Chemo-radiotherapy to Treat Operable Oesophageal Cancer

Collection in BBMRI Directory (URL)	study identifier	MDR Title
eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-153:collection:361-1018		
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-153:collection:361-1019	NCT01843829	A Feasibility Study of Chemo-radiotherapy to Treat Operable Oesophageal Cancer
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_AAAACW5FCXM3MZSUAVNCZ2AAAE:collection:EMC_2023_1429	NCT01851538	The Role of Biomarkers and Echocardiography in Prediction of Prognosis of Chronic Heart Failure Patients
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_AAAACXSW447PSACQK2MBZ5YAAM:collection:AAAACX5GLHKAACQK2MBZ5YAAE	NCT01898117	Triple-B Study; Carboplatin-cyclophosphamide Versus Paclitaxel With or Without Atezolizumab as First-line Treatment in Advanced Triple Negative Breast Cancer
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_AMCBB:collection:DC18-002	NCT01857856	PHOspholamban RELATED CARDIomyopathy Study - Intervention
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-108:collection:293-848	NCT01950689	NIMRAD: A randomised placebo-controlled trial of synchronous NIMorazole versus RADiotherapy alone in patients with locally advanced head and neck squamous cell carcinoma not suitable for synchronous chemotherapy or cetuximab
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_CRC:collection:10045	NCT01951521	RECTAL BOOST Study
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-153:collection:399-1126	NCT01992952	Fulvestrant +/- Akt Inhibition in Advanced Aromatase Inhibitor Resistant Breast Cancer
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-153:collection:399-1127	NCT01992952	Fulvestrant +/- Akt Inhibition in Advanced Aromatase Inhibitor Resistant Breast Cancer

Collection in BBMRI Directory (URL)	study identifier	MDR Title
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-114:collection:298-882	NCT01993979	A Phase III Randomised Trial of Peri-Operative Chemotherapy Versus sUrveillance in Upper Tract Urothelial Cancer (POUT)
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-114:collection:298-883	NCT01993979	A Phase III Randomised Trial of Peri-Operative Chemotherapy Versus sUrveillance in Upper Tract Urothelial Cancer (POUT)
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-114:collection:298-884	NCT01993979	A Phase III Randomised Trial of Peri-Operative Chemotherapy Versus sUrveillance in Upper Tract Urothelial Cancer (POUT)
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_AAAACXSW447PSACQK2MBZ5YAAM:collection:AAAACXSW45PG6ACQK2MBZ5YAAE	NCT01996267	Neoadjuvant Chemotherapy in HER2 Positive Breast Cancer, TRAIN-2
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:SE_2245:collection:all_samples	NCT02000076	The Stockholm Sleepy Brain Study: Effects of Sleep Deprivation on Cognitive and Emotional Processing in Young and Old
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-134:collection:1	NCT02057913	A Phase II Trial of Vinflunine Chemotherapy in locally-advanced and Metastatic Carcinoma of the Penis (VinCaP)
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_CRC:collection:10032	NCT02070146	Prospective Data Collection Initiative on Colorectal Cancer
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:SE_2388:collection:all_samples	NCT02078804	SCREESCO - Screening of Swedish Colons
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_CRC:collection:10009	NCT02162563	Treatment Strategies in Colorectal Cancer Patients with Initially Unresectable Liver-only Metastases

Collection in BBMRI Directory (URL)	study identifier	MDR Title
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-193:collection:1	NCT02183883	Deciphering Afatinib Response and Resistance With INtratour Heterogeneity (DARWIN1)
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_CRC:collection:10033	NCT02231086	Adjuvant HIPEC in High Risk Colon Cancer
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_CRC:collection:10011	NCT02243735	Trial Comparing Ferric(III)Carboxymaltose Infusion With Oral Iron Suppletion as Treatment of Anaemia
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_AAAACXSW447PSACQK2MBZ5YAAM:collection:AAAACXSW45D36ACQK2MBZ5YAAE	NCT02278887	Study Comparing TIL to Standard Ipilimumab in Patients With Metastatic Melanoma (TIL)
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-145:collection:388-1090	NCT02308722	SBRT Pre-operatively for Pancreatic Cancer
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-145:collection:388-1091	NCT02308722	SBRT Pre-operatively for Pancreatic Cancer
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-145:collection:388-1092	NCT02308722	SBRT Pre-operatively for Pancreatic Cancer
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-145:collection:388-1093	NCT02308722	SBRT Pre-operatively for Pancreatic Cancer
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-145:collection:388-1094	NCT02308722	SBRT Pre-operatively for Pancreatic Cancer

Collection in BBMRI Directory (URL)	study identifier	MDR Title
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-145:collection:388-1095	NCT02308722	SBRT Pre-operatively for Pancreatic Cancer
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-200:collection:1	NCT02315716	Carfilzomib/Cyclophosphamide/Dexamet hasone With Maintenance Carfilzomib in Multiple Myeloma (Cardamon)
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_AAAACXSW447PSACQK2MBZ5YAAM:collection:AAAACXSW45VXAACQK2MBZ5YAAE	NCT02362594	Study of Pembrolizumab (MK-3475) Versus Placebo After Complete Resection of High-Risk Stage III Melanoma (MK-3475-054/1325-MG/KEYNOTE-054)
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_CRC:collection:10030	NCT02371304	Rectal Preserving Treatment for Early Rectal Cancer. A Multi-centred Randomised Trial of Radical Surgery Versus Adjuvant Chemoradiotherapy After Local Excision for Early Rectal Cancers
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_AAAACXSW447PSACQK2MBZ5YAAM:collection:AAAACXSW46RFEACQK2MBZ5YAAI	NCT02375204	Standard-Dose Combination Chemotherapy or High-Dose Combination Chemotherapy and Stem Cell Transplant in Treating Patients With Relapsed or Refractory Germ Cell Tumors
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-186:collection:1	NCT02544308	Trial of Immunomodulatory Therapy in High Risk Solitary Bone Plasmacytoma
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_AAAACXSW447PSACQK2MBZ5YAAM:collection:AAAACXSW46AECACQK2MBZ5YAAE	NCT02625337	Study Comparing Pembrolizumab With Dual MAPK Pathway Inhibition Plus Pembrolizumab in Melanoma Patients
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_AMCBB:collection:AB15-006	NCT02646657	An Open Label Interventional Phase 4 Study to Evaluate Efficacy, Safety and Mucosal Healing of Early Versus Late Use of Vedolizumab in Ulcerative Colitis: the LOVE-UC Study (LOW Countries VEdolizumab in UC Study)

Collection in BBMRI Directory (URL)	study identifier	MDR Title
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_AMCBB:collection:AB15-006_1	NCT02646683	A Study to Evaluate Efficacy, of Early Versus Late Use of Vedolizumab in Crohn's Disease: the LOVE-CD Study
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_CRC:collection:10004	NCT02715141	Molecular stool testing for colorectal cancer surveillance
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:DE_IBBJ:collection:CANDISEP	NCT02734550	(1,3)- β -D-glucan Based Diagnosis of Invasive Candida Infection in Sepsis
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_CRC:collection:10010	NCT02758951	Perioperative Systemic Therapy for Isolated Resectable Colorectal Peritoneal Metastases
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_AAAACXSW447PSACQK2MBZ5YAAM:collection:AAAACYBR6IJTWACQK2MBZ5YAAE	NCT02826512	A Feasibility Study of Niraparib for Advanced, BRCA1-like, HER2-negative Breast Cancer Patients
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:AT_MUG:collection:ClinibilStudy	NCT02914782	Investigation of Fluid- and Electrolyte Balance in Post Cardiac-surgery Patients
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_AAAACXSW447PSACQK2MBZ5YAAM:collection:AAAACXSW46HH4ACQK2MBZ5YAAE	NCT02925234	The Drug Rediscovery Protocol (DRUP Trial)
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_CRC:collection:10034	NCT02945566	Can the Rectum be Saved by Watchful Waiting or TransAnal Surgery Following (Chemo)Radiotherapy Versus Total Mesorectal Excision for Early REctal Cancer?
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_CRC:collection:10035	NCT02945566	Can the Rectum be Saved by Watchful Waiting or TransAnal Surgery Following (Chemo)Radiotherapy Versus Total Mesorectal Excision for Early REctal Cancer?

Collection in BBMRI Directory (URL)	study identifier	MDR Title
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-146:collection:370-1112	NCT03004755	The PEACE (Posthumous Evaluation of Advanced Cancer Environment) Study
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:AT_MUG:collection:EmmyStudy	NCT03087773	Impact of EMPagliflozin on Cardiac Function and Biomarkers of Heart Failure in Patients With Acute MYocardial Infarction
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_CRC:collection:10013	NCT03088150	COLLISION Trial - Colorectal Liver Metastases: Surgery vs Thermal Ablation
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_AAAACXSW447PSACQK2MBZ5YAAM:collection:AAAACX7OHVVRMACQK2MBZ5YAAE	NCT03147040	AssessinG Efficacy of Carboplatin and ATezOlizumab in Metastatic Lobular Breast Cancer: GELATO-trial
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_AMCBB:collection:AB16-016	NCT03158727	Clinical trial to study the effects and safety of stem cells, derived from fat tissue from human donors, administered intravenously to treat patients with severe bacterial pneumonia acquired outside the hospital, nursing home or long-term care facilities. Admitted to the Intensive Care Unit
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_CRC:collection:10053	NCT03191110	The COLON Study: Colorectal Cancer Cohort
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_AAAACW5ELBQ4WZSUAVNCZ2AAAE:collection:187	NCT03303833	The GEOLynch Cohort Study
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_CRC:collection:10052	NCT03303833	The GEOLynch Cohort Study

Collection in BBMRI Directory (URL)	study identifier	MDR Title
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_CRC:collection:10002	NCT03413254	Second and Third Look Laparoscopy in pT4 Colon Cancer Patients for Early Detection of Peritoneal Metastases
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-145:collection:391-1108	NCT03529669	Cytosponge™ for Post-Chemoradiation Surveillance of Oesophageal Cancer
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-145:collection:391-1109	NCT03529669	Cytosponge™ for Post-Chemoradiation Surveillance of Oesophageal Cancer
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-145:collection:391-1110	NCT03529669	Cytosponge™ for Post-Chemoradiation Surveillance of Oesophageal Cancer
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-145:collection:391-1111	NCT03529669	Cytosponge™ for Post-Chemoradiation Surveillance of Oesophageal Cancer
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:DE_IBBJ:collection:KoALA	NCT03558776	Influence of the Background Diet on Metabolism of Land-based n-3 PUFA
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-179:collection:1	NCT03562169	The Role of Ixazomib in Autologous Stem Cell Transplant in Relapsed Myeloma - Myeloma XII (ACCoRd)
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-145:collection:390-1104	NCT03641547	M6620 Plus Standard Treatment in Oesophageal and Other Cancer
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-145:collection:390-1105	NCT03641547	M6620 Plus Standard Treatment in Oesophageal and Other Cancer
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-	NCT03641547	M6620 Plus Standard Treatment in Oesophageal and Other Cancer

Collection in BBMRI Directory (URL)	study identifier	MDR Title
eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-145:collection:390-1106		
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:UK_GBR-1-145:collection:390-1107	NCT03641547	M6620 Plus Standard Treatment in Oesophageal and Other Cancer
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_AAAACW5FCXM3MZSUAVNCZ2AAAE:collection:EMC_CB_IMPORT_2021_24	NCT03703947	Biomarker Profiling in Abdominal Aortic Aneurysm Patients
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_CRC:collection:10019	NCT03737539	Dynamic Monitoring of ctDNA Methylation to Predict Relapse in Colorectal Cancer After Radical Resection
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:DE_UMGB:collection:ROCK-ALS	NCT03792490	Inhibition of Rho Kinase (ROCK) With Fasudil as Disease-modifying Treatment for ALS
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_AAAACW5FCXM3MZSUAVNCZ2AAAE:collection:EMC_2023_3160	NCT03872778	NeoRay - Phase I/IIa trial of [177Lu]-NeoB in patients with advanced solid tumors and with [68Ga]-NeoB lesion uptake.
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_RB:collection:169	NCT03909724	Pulsatile High-dose Sunitinib Versus TAS-102 in Patients With Metastatic Colorectal Carcinoma (mCRC)
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_AMCBB:collection:AB20-012	NCT03961438	Amsterdam UMC Clinical Trial With a Native-like HIV-1 Envelope Vaccine
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_CRC:collection:10005	NCT04004650	Gluteal Turnover Flap for Closure of the Perineal Wound After Abdominoperineal Resection for Rectal Cancer
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_CRC:collection:10014	NCT04081168	COLLISION XL: Unresectable Colorectal Liver Metastases (3-5cm): Stereotactic Body Radiotherapy vs. Microwave Ablation

Collection in BBMRI Directory (URL)	study identifier	MDR Title
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:CH_UniversitatsspitalBasel:collection:CH_MATAO	NCT04111978	Maintenance Therapy with Aromatase Inhibitor in Epithelial Ovarian Cancer (MATAO)
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_AAAACW5FCXM3MZSUAVNCZ2AAAE:collection:EMC_2023_7392	NCT04119440	Safety and Immunogenicity of the Candidate Vaccine MVA-MERS-S_DF-1 Against MERS
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_AAAACXSW447PSACQK2MBZ5YAAM:collection:aaaaczxxvjr4acqk2m06qaae	NCT04193956	POINTING: Clinical Cohort Study of Patients With Melanoma and NSCLC Receiving Checkpoint Inhibitors
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_AAAACW5FCXM3MZSUAVNCZ2AAAE:collection:EMC_CB_IMPORT_2021_17	NCT04256473	Dual Thrombolytic Therapy With Mutant Pro-urokinase and Low Dose Alteplase for Ischemic Stroke
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_RB:collection:183	NCT04302454	Androgen Deprivation Therapy for Oligo-recurrent Prostate Cancer in Addition to radioTherapy
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_AAAACW5FCXM3MZSUAVNCZ2AAAE:collection:EMC_2023_7704	NCT04342182	Convalescent Plasma as Therapy for Covid-19 Severe SARS-CoV-2 Disease (CONCOVID Study)
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_AAAACW5FCXM3MZSUAVNCZ2AAAE:collection:EMC_CB_IMPORT_2021_16	NCT04373902	Physiological-based Cord Clamping in Congenital Diaphragmatic Hernia
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:DE_UMGB:collection:BioVAT-HF	NCT04396899	Safety and Efficacy of Induced Pluripotent Stem Cell-derived Engineered Human Myocardium as Biological Ventricular Assist Tissue in Terminal Heart Failure

Collection in BBMRI Directory (URL)	study identifier	MDR Title
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_AAAACW5FCXM3MZSUAVNCZ2AAAE:collection:EMC_2023_7967	NCT04489160	Complement Inhibition: Attacking the Overshooting Inflammation @Fter Traumatic Brain Injury
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_AMCBB:collection:AB21-013	NCT04507178	Improving Outcome in Subarachnoid Hemorrhage wth Nadroparine.
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_CRC:collection:10047	NCT04552093	Hepatic Arterial Infusion Pump Chemotherapy Combined With Systemic Chemotherapy (PUMP-IT)
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:AT_MUG:collection:ProbioticdietaryInterventioninPolycysticOvarySyndrome	NCT04593459	Probiotic Intervention in PCOS
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:AT_MUG:collection:TheCoVVacStudy:COVID-19vaccinationimmunocompromisedhealthy-cellagingt-cellimmunityhumoralandcellularimmuneresponse	NCT04858607	Humoral and Cellular Immune Response to COVID-19 Vaccines in Immunocompromised and Healthy Individuals
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_AAAACW5FCXM3MZSUAVNCZ2AAAE:collection:EMC_CB_IMPORT_2021_06	NCT04876716	Azole-echinocandin Combination Therapy for Invasive Aspergillosis
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_AAAACW5FCXM3MZSUAVNCZ2AAAE:collection:EMC_2023_3615	NCT04878770	NMF biomarker as predictive diagnostic for effective use of ciclosporine in atopic dermatitis.
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_AAAACW5FCXM3MZSUAVNCZ2AAAE:collection:EMC_2023_3871	NCT04888754	A Prospective Cohort for ex Vivo Cure Studies With Chronic HIV Infected Patients in the Netherlands: The CHRONO Project

Collection in BBMRI Directory (URL)	study identifier	MDR Title
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_AAAACW5FCXM3MZSUAVNCZ2AAAE:collection:EMC_2023_6880	NCT04927780	Perioperative or Adjuvant mFOLFIRINOX for Resectable Pancreatic Cancer
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_AMCBB:collection:AB21-016	NCT04990232	ImmunoSep Personalized Immunotherapy in Sepsis
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_CRC:collection:10048	NCT05092880	Radioembolization in Elderly/ Fragile Patients With mCRC
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:AT_MUG:collection:TheCoVVacBoostStudy-COVID-19boostervaccination	NCT05142540	Detection and Characterization of Anti-SARS-CoV-2 Salivary Antibodies After COVID-19 Booster Vaccines
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_AAAACW5FCXM3MZSUAVNCZ2AAAE:collection:EMC_2023_7240	NCT05228574	Treatment of Vascular Stiffness in ADPKD
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:DE_UMGB:collection:Reduce-MFA	NCT05230901	Reduce-MFA
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_AAAACW5FCXM3MZSUAVNCZ2AAAE:collection:EMC_2023_8792	NCT05364411	Hypofractionated, Dose-redistributed RAdiotherapy With Protons and Photons in HNSCC
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_AAAACW5FCXM3MZSUAVNCZ2AAAE:collection:EMC_CB_IMPORT_2021_11	NCT05524259	MYPP-trial: Myo-inositol Supplementation to Prevent Pregnancy Complications in Women With Polycystic Ovary Syndrome.
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_AAAACW5FCXM3MZSUAVNCZ2AAAE:collection:EMC_2023_8383	NCT05525338	Comparison of Standard Dose Alectinib to Alectinib in Adjusted Dose Based on Alectinib Bloodlevels

Collection in BBMRI Directory (URL)	study identifier	MDR Title
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_AAAACW5FCXM3MZSUAVNCZ2AAAE:collection:EMC_2023_7882	NCT05564845	Brain Structure and Neurocognitive Development in Sickle Cell Disease; a Longitudinal Cohort Study (BRICK Study)
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_AAAACW5FCXM3MZSUAVNCZ2AAAE:collection:EMC_2023_8053	NCT05637099	The Value of Repeated BIOMarker Measurements During an SBT to Predict Extubation Failure in ICU Patients
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_AAAACW5FCXM3MZSUAVNCZ2AAAE:collection:EMC_2023_7973	NCT05754645	The PROMOTE Study, a Pilot: The Characterization of the Microbiome in Pregnancy and Prediction of Pregnancy Outcomes
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_AMCBB:collection:AB14-002	NL1046	IMPRESS in STEMI
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_AAAACXPKLWV6CACQK2ME25QAEE:collection:44	NL1520	Implementation of a health education and risk prediction program for parents (WHeezing Illnesses Study LEidsche Rijn (WHISTLER)-online) to reduce ineffective primary health care consumption for respiratory illnesses in children during the first year of life.
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_AMCBB:collection:AB17-001	NL280	The incidence of post-trauma psychopathology study (TRAUMA TIPS): efficacy of an innovative preventive multimedia intervention
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_AAAACXJQEK6I4ACQK2ME25QAEE:collection:aaaac2dvtrwmuacqk2mpm4yaae	NL2899	The Active and Healthy Aging Study (Dutch: Actief en Gezond Oud Studie).
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_AAAACW5FCXM3MZSUAVNCZ2AAAE:collection:EMC_2023_6388	NL4365	Pancreatic Cyst Follow-up, an International Collaboration, PACYFIC study A prospective evaluation of pancreatic cyst surveillance, based on the consensus statement, formulated by the

Collection in BBMRI Directory (URL)	study identifier	MDR Title
		European study group on cystic tumours of the pancreas
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_AAAACXPASAS2AACQK2ME25QAAE:collection:aaaac2lq6ovnr6qwh3r gblaaae	NL4465	Self-monitoring and personalized feedback as a tool to boost depression treatment
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_AAAACW5FCXM3MZSUAVNCZ2AAAE:collection:EMC_2023_7727	NL5129	COBRA3 (COngenital heart defects: BRidging the gap between growth, maturation, Regeneration, Adaptation, late Attrition and Ageing) We want to research the effects of growth, maturation and regeneration on the aging of the heart in patients with a congenital heart defect.
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_AAAACXPASAS2AACQK2ME25QAAE:collection:aaaac3gmy3aod6qwh3rgblaaae	NL5194	Learning by moving
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_AAAACVOEPHI3IZSUAVNCZ2AAAE:collection:DC15-002	NL5255	Amsterdam Case-control study in Thrombosis 2
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_CRC:collection:10003	NL5368	Pelvic Floor rehabilitation to improve functional Outcome and quality of life after surgery for Rectal CancEr: a randomized trial.
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_AAAACVOEPHI3IZSUAVNCZ2AAAE:collection:DC16-006	NL5439	Discovery and validation of diagnostic biomarkers for left ventricular diastolic dysfunction and HEart failUre with Preserved circulation ejection Fraction
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_CRC:collection:10049	NL5784	Prehabilitation for bowel cancer patients undergoing surgery to improve fitness and reduce complications

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https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_AMCBB:collection:AB17-022	NL6145	Physical Activity and Dietary intervention in OVArian cancer (PADOVA)
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_AMCBB:collection:AB16-010	NL6213	A trial to compare if the diseased area between the colon and the small bowel of patients with Crohn's disease stays free of disease after surgery between a group of patients whom receive no medication versus a group whom receive vedolizumab
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_CRC:collection:10018	NL6281	Prevention of recurrent disease by additional chemotherapy in patients with detectable circulating tumor DNA in the blood after surgery for stage II (lymph nodes unaffected) colon cancer.
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_CRC:collection:10050	NL6408	Experienced Quality of Care and Life in advanced oncological patients and their relatives: a prospective observational cohort study
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_CRC:collection:10017	NL6904	Energy for life after ColoRectal cancer: The EnCoRe study
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_CRC:collection:10029	NL6988	Concomitant intraperitoneal and systemic chemotherapy in patients with extensive peritoneal carcinomatosis of colorectal origin
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_CRC:collection:10027	NL7072	Uniform Noting for International application of the Tumour-stroma ratios Easy Diagnostic tool
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_AAAACXPASAS2AACQK2ME25QAAE:collection:aaaac4m4dudrf6qwh3rgblaaae	NL7262	Validation of [11C]MeDAS PET imaging for myelin quantification in multiple sclerosis

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https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_CRC:collection:10012	NL7277	Adjuvant hepatic arterial infusion pump chemotherapy after resection of colorectal liver metastases in patients with a low clinical risk score – a randomized controlled trial
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_CRC:collection:10022	NL7305	Organoids to Predict Treatment response In mCRC (OPTIC)
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_AAAACVOEPHI3IZSUAVNCZ2AAAE:collection:DC19-002	NL7430	Hemodynamic Monitoring with the CardioMEMS PA sensor and Quality of Life in Patients with Chronic Heart Failure:
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_AMCBB:collection:DC19-005	NL7546	Vasospastic angina treatment by Endothelin Receptor Antagonism; a proof of concept study
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_50:collection:aaaacy3d3llht6qwh3e73dqaba	NL7839	OncoLifeS Oncological Life Study: Living well as a cancer survivor
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_AAAACW5FCXM3MZSUAVNCZ2AAAE:collection:EMC_2023_6297	NL7966	Fecal Immunochemical Testing as a Tool to Determine the Need for Colonoscopy in Symptomatic Patients
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_CRC:collection:10007	NL8039	Clinical added value of MRI over CT in patients scheduled for local colorectal liver metastases therapy
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_CRC:collection:10023	NL8177	A study on the response to neoadjuvant chemotherapy per CMS subtype in patients with colon cancer
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_CRC:collection:10006	NL8261	Multi-Interventional program for prevention and early Management of Anastomotic leakage after total mesorectal excision in Rectal cancer patients, the IMARI-trial

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https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_CRC:collection:10039	NL8303	Bidirectional treatment consisting of repetitive laparoscopic electrostatic pressurized intraperitoneal aerosol chemotherapy with oxaliplatin (ePIPAC-OX) and systemic intravenous chemotherapy for isolated unresectable colorectal peritoneal metastases: feasibility, safety, tolerability, and preliminary efficacy.
https://directory.bbmri-eric.eu/#/collection/bbmri-eric:ID:NL_CRC:collection:10044	NL9294	Adjuvant hepatic arterial infusion pump chemotherapy after repeat hepatectomy for patients with liver confined recurrence of colorectal cancer – a phase II study